

Clinical Study of Newly Diagnosed HIV Patients with Special Reference to Skin Manifestations and Its Correlation with CD4 Counts**Rajesh Kumar Dhanowar¹, Malisetty Sreenivas Sai², Aditya Poddar³, Shravan S M⁴, Siddhant Kumar⁵**¹Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh (Assam)
²M.D, General Medicine^{3,4,5}Post Graduate Trainees, Department of Medicine, Assam Medical, College and Hospital, Dibrugarh (Assam)

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Aditya Poddar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** It is found that skin problems are always compounded together with the high prevalence of HIV. 90% of the people living with HIV have changes in their skin and symptoms during the disease course. HIV associated skin diseases were related to multiple factors like differences in skin pigmentation, genetic, climate, hygiene, demographic, environmental, behavioral factors etc. Many studies have found the correlation between the CD4 counts and the mucocutaneous lesions. Some studies have also found the correlation of the disease with the Clinical stage. The main aim of the study is to study the clinical profile of the newly diagnosed HIV patients with the mucocutaneous lesions and to find its correlation with the CD4 cell counts.**Methods:** The study was carried out at Assam Medical College & Hospital, Dibrugarh, India for a period of 12 months. A prospective, observational, cross-sectional, study was carried out in the inpatient and outpatient medicine departments. The total sample size was calculated to be 90.**Results:** Most of the dermatological manifestations were common in the CD4 counts between 201-500 Group III with 45 cases followed by 50-200 Group II where the cases were 22 indicating that skin manifestations like oral candidiasis occur early in the disease and requires screening for HIV. Among the skin manifestations statistically significant association with the CD4 counts was found in Oral candidiasis ($p=0.02$), Genital Herpes ($p=0.04$) and Pruritic papular manifestations ($p<0.001$).**Conclusion:** it is concluded that the mucocutaneous manifestations can serve as a prognostic and diagnostic marker for the HIV disease. We can also easily predict the stage of the disease and the immune status and can start the treatment which will tend to decrease the morbidity and will increase the quality of life.**Keywords:** HIV, CD4 Counts, Skin Manifestation.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

From 1981 HIV/AIDS has been one of the diseases which was a continuous threat to mankind. According to an estimation in 2017 in India the prevalence of HIV among adults was estimated to be 0.22%. In 2018 nearly 37.9 million were living with HIV at global level. Among the People living with HIV infection it was found that 42% were females and 97% belonged to age of above 15 years. In the year 2017, 87.58 thousand people were found to be newly diagnosed with HIV and 69.11 thousand people died from AIDS related causes in the same year. [1] Human Immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection spreads sexually through blood or its products or from infected mother to her child during pregnancy or breastfeeding through vertical transmission. The virus generally affects the immunocompetent cells

like CD4 cells and the Macrophages. [2] Thus AIDS is considered as a group of symptoms or disease due to HIV infection which is due to the decreased lymphocytic cell counts. The main target of the HIV infection is the subset of lymphocytes which is produced by the thymus known as Helper T cells which is essential for the cellular immunity. The immune status of the adults and children with HIV will be assessed by measuring the CD4+ Cell counts which is the standard way for assessing the severity of the disease. [3,4] It is found that skin problems are always compounded together with the high prevalence of HIV. 90% of the people living with HIV have changes in their skin and symptoms during the disease course. [5,6] We found significantly higher skin diseases in people living with HIV positive than the HIV negative

individuals through extensive review of literature. HIV associated skin diseases were related to multiple factors like differences in skin pigmentation, genetic, climate, hygiene, demographic, environmental, behavioral factors etc. [7,8] Skin infections and mucosal changes of HIV patient should be known to everyone. The first manifestation of the HIV infection is the mucosal changes as it is due to the CD4 cells which is also present in the Langerhan cells. These Langerhan cells are also known as Antigen presenting cells (APC). Langerhan cells are present in the mucosa and the epithelium of the skin. These mucosal changes help us in diagnosing early and starting the treatment promptly preventing the complications. Thus the health care provider should be aware about the prevalence of the skin diseases in their area, type, pattern etc. [9,10] Many studies have found the correlation between the CD4 counts and the Mucocutaneous lesions. [11,12] Some studies have also found the correlation of the disease with the Clinical stage.¹³ The cutaneous disorders are seen in the all stages of the diseases and it ranges from the opportunistic infection and inflammatory dermatoses to the cutaneous malignancies. The cutaneous manifestation which usually occur in the patients are xerosis, ichthyosis, pruritis, folliculitis, prurigo, pruritic papular eruptions, eosinophilic folliculitis, Psoriasis, Seborrheic dermatitis, herpes simplex, herpes zoster, oral and vaginal candidiasis, tinea, scabies, squamous cell carcinoma, basal cell carcinoma and Kaposi sarcoma. Among the HIV patients drug reactions are also common. The main aim of the study is to study the clinical profile of the newly diagnosed HIV patients with the mucocutaneous lesions and to find its correlation with the CD4 cell counts

Aim: To study the clinical profile of newly diagnosed HIV patients with special reference to dermatological manifestations.

Objective:

- To evaluate the clinical presentation of newly diagnosed HIV patients.
- To study the pattern of skin involvement and its features
- To estimate the CD4 counts in the cases.
- To find out the various skin manifestations with respect to stage, CD4 counts and its correlation.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out at Assam Medical College & Hospital, Dibrugarh, India for a period of 12 months. A prospective, observational, cross-sectional, study was carried out in the inpatient and outpatient medicine departments. The total sample size was calculated to be 90. The protocol was approved by the institutional ethics

committee. The subjects agreed to sign a formal informed consent form covering the details of the research. The medical history and patient profile questionnaires were used to collect the patient's data.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All the patients aged above 13 years of both sexes.
- Patients diagnosed as HIV through ELISA or Rapid test as per NACO guidelines with at least one skin manifestation.
- Patients giving written informed consent and willing to participate in the study

Exclusion criteria

- Patient aged less than 13 years. □
- Known HIV cases already on HAART. □
- HIV positive patients taking antitubercular therapy.
- HIV positive patients taking antibiotic therapy in last two weeks. Patient not giving consent for participating in the study

Data Collection: After obtaining the permission from the Institute of Ethical Committee, the informed written consent of all the study participants was obtained. All the study participants were evaluated thorough clinical history, physical examination and appropriate investigations apart from routine investigations like eg, KOH preparation of nail clippings, Tzanck smear were done, PCR for HSV were done for the required patients.

Demographic Details: Study participants Name, Age, Sex, Marital status, Education, Occupation, and Mode of transmission were documented. □

Clinical Assessment: Clinical assessment was done separately in a predesigned proforma where the patients were staged as per WHO guidelines.

HIV Diagnosis: The HIV was confirmed as per the NACO guidelines CD4 Estimation: With the help of the FACS (Fluorescent Activated cell counter) CD 4+ cell counts were done

Diagnostic Tests: For certain mucocutaneous manifestations specific tests were done. For Example: Herpes infection –PCR, Tzanck smear, Onychomycosis- KOH preparation of nail clippings for the required patients, Chest X-Ray, sputum CBNAAT for tuberculosis.

Statistical Analysis: After collecting the data it was entered in MS Excel Windows 10. Statistical analysis was done in SPSS 23. Continuous data were expressed in terms of Mean± Standard deviation and Categorical variables were expressed in terms of numbers (percentages). Chi square test was used for Test of Association for Categorical variables. Anova test or Student t test was used for

Test of Association for Continuous variables. P value of <0.05 is considered to be statistically significant

Results:

1. Baseline Characteristics of the study participants:

Table 1: Age distribution of the study participants

Age Category	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
<19 years	7	7.7
20-29 years	38	42.2
30-39 years	21	23.3
40-49 years	14	15.5
50-59 years	4	4.4
>60 years	6	6.6
Total	90	100

Majority of the study participants 38(42.2%) were in the 20-29 years of age category followed by 21(23.3%) 30-39 years of age. Only 6(6.6%) were above 60 years.

Figure 1: Mean age of the study participants

The mean age of our study participants was found to be 34.07±13.27 with minimum as 15 years and maximum age as 70 years. Figure–2: Sex distribution of the study participants

Figure 2: Sex distribution among the study

In our study majority of the study participants were male 53(58.9%) followed by Females 37(41.1%).

Table 2: Education status of the study participants

Education status	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Graduate	8	8.9
High school	7	7.8
Middle school	7	7.8
Primary	4	4.4
Illiterate	64	71.1
Total	90	100

Only 4 (4.4%) of the study participants completed primary education and 7 (7.8%) have completed their middle school and high school education. In our study most of the participants were illiterate 64 (71.1%) followed by Graduate 8 (8.9%)

Table 3: Occupation of the study participant

Occupation	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Skilled	45	50
Semiskilled	8	8.9
Manual labour	25	27.8
Student	3	3.3
Unemployed	9	10
Total	90	100

Among the study participants majority were Skilled workers 45(50%) followed by the Manual labour 25(27.8%).According to our study 9(10%) of the study participants were unemployed and 3(3.3%) were students with the majority falling under the category of skilled labour 45 (50%).

Table 3: Marital status of the study participants:

Marital Status	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Married	72	80
Unmarried	11	12.2
Widow/Widower	7	7.8
Total	90	100

In our study 7(7.8%) were widow or widower whereas 11(12.2%) were unmarried with the rest of the participants married 72(80%).

Table 5: Modes of transmission:

Modes of transmission	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Heterosexual	77	85.6
Blood transfusion	3	3.3
Unknown	10	11.1
Total	90	100

Majority were infected through heterosexual mode of transmission 77(85.6%) followed by unknown mode 10(11.1%). Only negligible number 3(3.3%) were infected through blood transfusion.

Table 6: Distribution of the HIV patients based on Symptoms:

	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Fever	36	40%
Weight loss	34	37.7%
Cough	7	7.7%
Decreased appetite	7	7.7%
Diarrhoea	2	2.2%
Asymptomatic	4	4.4%
Total	90	100

The most common symptom was Fever 36(40%) followed by weight loss 34(37.7%).The third most common symptom is Anorexia and Cough 7(8%). Diarrhea is the least common presentation 2(2.2%).

II Clinical staging of the HIV patients based on WHO classification

Table 7: Clinical staging of the HIV patients

Clinical staging	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Stage 1	3	3.33
Stage 2	32	35.5
Stage 3	43	47.7
Stage 4	12	13.3
Total	90	100

Most of the study participants belongs to stage 3 classification 43(47.7%) followed by stage2 32(35.5%).

Figure 3: Clinical staging of the HIV patients

Majority of the study participants belongs to stage 3 and stage 2 classifications.

Table 8: Classification of patients according to the WHO immunological staging of HIV:

WHO immunological staging, CD4 counts	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
<50/mm ³	3	3.3%
50-200/mm ³	22	24.5%
201-500/mm ³	45	50%
>500/mm ³	20	22.2%
Total	90	100

Among the study participants majority 45(50%) were having CD4 counts ranging between 201-500/mm³ followed by 50-200/mm³ cells 22(24.5%).

Figure 4: Immunological staging of HIV among the study participants

20 (22.2%) of the study participants have cells >500/mm³ whereas 3(3.3%) have CD4 cells ranging from <50 /mm³

Table 9: Prevalence of Common Infectious dermatoses among the study population:

Dermatoses	Number (N)	Percentages (%)
Oral Candidiasis	31	34
Vaginal discharge syndrome	10	11
Tinea	7	8
Genital herpes	7	8
Herpes zoster	6	7
Genital wart	5	6
Pruritic papular eruptions	4	4.4
Herpes zoster Ophthalmicus	4	4.4
Xerosis	3	3.3
Scabies	3	3.3
Psoriasis	3	3.3
Seborrheic dermatitis	3	3.3
Onychomycosis	2	2
Recurrent oral ulcers	2	2
Total	90	100

The most common infection was Oral candidiasis 31(34%) which is followed by vaginal discharge syndrome 10(11%).The third most common infection is Tinea and Genital herpes 7(8%).

Figure 5: Prevalence of Common Infectious dermatoses among the study population:

Table 10: Association of infectious Dermatoses and the CD4 count

Clinical manifestations	<50	50-200	201-500	>500	Total	Chi square/ Fischer	P value
Oral Candidiasis	1	12	13	5	31	4.725	0.02*
Vaginal discharge syndrome	0	5	5	0	10	2.76	0.09
Tinea	1	3	2	1	7	3.26	0.07
Genital herpes	0	0	3	4	7	4.01	0.04*
Herpes zoster	0	0	2	4	6	3.38	0.06
Genital wart	0	1	3	1	5	0.15	0.68
Pruritic papular eruptions	0	4	0	0	4		<0.001*
Herpes zoster ophthalmicus	0	0	2	2	4	1.61	0.20
Xerosis	0	1	1	1	3	0.41	0.82
Scabies	0	1	2	0	3	0.41	0.82
Psoriasis	0	1	2	0	3	0.41	0.82
Seborrheic dermatitis	0	1	2	0	3	0.41	0.82
Onychomycosis	0	0	1	1	2	0.78	0.37
Recurrent oral ulcers	0	0	1	1	2	0.78	0.37
Total	3	22	45	20	90		

Among the study participants oral candidiasis, Genital herpes and pruritic papular eruption found to be statistically significant.

Figure 6: Genital Warts

Figure 7: Onychomycosis

Figure 8: Herpes Zoster

Figure 9: Pruritic Papular Eruption

Figure 10: Oral Candida (Left), Oral Candidiasis with Erosions (Right)

Figure 11: Psoriasis

Figure 12: Herpes Genital Ulcer

Figure 13: Tinea Corporis

Conclusion

The results of our study stated that there is a correlation between the skin manifestations and the CD4 counts both in severity and presentation with fungal infections being the overall common dermatological manifestation with the majority of patients scattered in WHO clinical stages 2 and 3 followed by viral infections especially during the early stages of HIV. Thus screening for HIV have to be done if the patients present with the said skin manifestations for the early diagnosis and treatment in order to avoid these infectious and non-infectious dermatoses in terms of frequency, severity and the disease progression in itself.

Thus it is concluded that the mucocutaneous manifestations can serve as a prognostic and diagnostic marker for the HIV disease. We can also easily predict the stage of the disease and the immune status and can start the treatment which will tend to decrease the morbidity and will increase the quality of life.

Bibliography

1. NACO India HIV Estimation 2017; <http://naco.gov.in/data-analysis-and-dissemination-unit-o>.
2. Christopher E.M, Griffith, Jonathan Barker, Tanya Bliker, Robert Chalmers DC. Rook's textbook of Dermatology.9th edition. USA: John wiley & Sons. 2016;
3. Chopra S AU. Skin and Mucocutaneous Manifestations: Useful Clinical Predictors of HIV/AIDS. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2012; 6(10):1695–8.
4. Lipworth AD, Freeman EE SA. Cutaneous Manifestations of HIV and Human T-Lympho tropic Virus. In Kang S, Amagai M, Bruckner AL, Enk AH, Margolis DJ, Mc Michael AJ, Orringer JS eds. MacGraw Hill. Fitzpatrick's Dermatology. 2019; 9e.
5. AM ND. Cutaneous manifestation of HIV/AIDS Part I. *South Afr J HIV Med.* 2004; 5:12–7.
6. J.Hu, K, Mckoy AP. Dermatology and HIV/AIDS in Africa. *J Glob Infect Dis.* 2011; 3(3):275–80.
7. BK Gow, R.KW Chan P Sen. Spectrum of skin disorders in human immunodeficiency virus infected patients in Singapore and the relationship to CD4 lymphocytes count. *Int J Dermatol.* 2007; 46(7):695–9.
8. EH Amerson TM. Dermatological manifestations of HIV in Africa. *Top HIV Med.* 2010; 18(1):16–22.
9. CL Kovarik, A Kekitiinwa HS. Cutaneous manifestations of HIV infections. *HIV Curric Heal Prof.*
10. Jordaan H. Common Skin and mucosal disorders in HIV/AIDS. *South African Fam Pract.* 2008; 50(6):14–23.
11. PV Raju, GR Rao, TV Ramini SV. Skin disease: Clinical indicator of immune status in human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection. *Int J Dermatol.* 2005; 44(8):646–9.
12. World Health Organization, WHO Case definitions of HIV for Surveillance and Revised Clinical staging and Immunological Classification of HIV Related diseases in Adults and Children. World Health Organisation, Geneva, Switzerland. 2006;
13. Nnoruka E. Skin diseases in south east nigeria: A current perspective. *Int J Dermatol.* 20 05; 44:29–33.